

Exploring the Connection between Influencer Marketing and Consumer Purchase Decision in Fashion Industry

Shabrina Zata Amani, Asad Ur Rehman Muhammad Sadiq, Iis Mariam
Graduate School of Management, Management and Science University

Abstract: *This paper aims to investigate the concept of influencer marketing in fashion while demonstrating how the actions of influencers marketing on purchase decision. As customers' disposable incomes and credits increase, the pressure on the fashion industry is increasing to adopt more sustainable practices taking into account the social and environmental cost of fast fashion industry business models. Through many forms of media available, influencer marketing plays an important role in educating consumers on sustainable fashion as well as, rational usage. Nonetheless, to achieve this goal, brands must work only with influencers who have comparable values and help users make a change toward sustainable consumption. Furthermore, there is also the issue of identifying the right influencers who are capable of building touch with the audience. As identified, this research seeks to evaluate influencers and their decisions based on fashion marketing. With these insights, brands can then move to improve brand image, and optimize the conversion of the consumers by applying influencer marketing. Additionally, this study adds to the body of knowledge in B2B marketing by examining the influence of digital influencers when selecting a vendor, as well as offering managerial implications for brands and agencies targeting to optimize influencer marketing.*

Keywords: *Consumer Purchase Decision, Influencer Marketing, Fashion.*

INTRODUCTION

Fashion can be a way through which consumers communicate by either embracing established trends or styles. This time it is primarily stimulated by the increase in disposable income and credit accessibility. The pressure to become more sustainable is increasing because the Industry has consequences at the social and environmental level due to fast fashion business models and overconsumption. However, given shifting consumer trends in this ever-changing world, influencer marketing acts as a key opinion shaper regarding what consumers should purchase. That is why with the help of posting truthful content, influencers are able to inform enough consumers about sustainable fashion and rational consumption. However, as the credibility of influencers and their activity vary, brands need to work with influencers who share their and their target customers values. Since this alignment can increase the effectiveness of the marketing disciplines, in turn it can strengthen the consumer's trust to shift the buying habits in the fashion industry towards more sustainable consumption. (Johnstone, L., & Lindh, C., 2022)

It is equally important to identify and target the right audience within social media with influence to turn potential customers to actual customers, through the creation of quality and genuine content. However, the influence of social media in influencing customer decisions has shifted and it is difficult for brands to find influencers, who have good reputation in promoting products. One of the biggest problems companies need to overcome is tied to identifying the right influencers, those who reflect company's values and at the same time, reflect the buyer personas and can help to affect purchase decisions. It is of much importance for this alignment because it is a way of creating a sense of mutual trust and consistency that helps customers respond and convert. With the increasing challenges that characterise

influencer marketing, brands are forced to unravel these difficulties in order to establish real relationship with customers. (Venciute, D., et al., 2023)

This study aims to fill this gap by assessing the factors that determine influencer marketing towards to fashion and the influence of influencer marketing on purchase decision. Influence marketing has become one of the essential tactics for reaching consumers, especially in the fashion industry, where the right influencers can most definitely influence consumers' buying behaviors. One task appears to be especially difficult, and that is the process of discovering relevant influencers that share a similar set of values of the given brand and are able to persuade their audience. When it comes to assessment factors, there is a range of numeric parameters, including followers, likes, comments, and credibility as well as expertise. Thus, recognizing how these factors impact the consumer attitude, the brands will benefit from this kind of promotion to reshape and maximize the influencer marketing's potential to improve the brand image and achieve long-term consumer conversion. (Chetioui, Y., et al, 2020)

The results of this study are expected to contribute to the B2B marketing literature because it asks a question that has not been considered before to the best of the authors' knowledge, namely the use of influencer marketing in the evaluation and selection of vendors. With social media stars emerging as more dominant forces for brands and businesses, assessing the effect that these individuals have on choice of vendors is critical. From the managerial standpoint, the authors were able to identify how managers view the stereotypes attached to influencer marketing and how those perceptions can affect the decision of which vendor to choose. Consequently, this paper presents the following strategic recommendations for vendor companies and agencies seeking to incorporate the B2B digital influencer marketing as a marketing tool as well as for the B2B digital influencers themselves. Through exploring this relation, we seek to improve the current knowledge of the place and role that influencer marketing occupies within B2B settings and its consequences for decision-making. (Crisafulli, B., & Singh, J., 2022)

1.1 Literature Review

1.1.1 Consumer Purchase Decision

Buyer behaviour decision process also known as consumer purchase decision involves the decision making process by the consumer when selecting a product to purchase satisfying certain needs. According to Chetioui, Benlafqih, and Lebdaoui (2020) within the context of fashion, is defined as a construal of products in relation to personal factors, in this case personal identity, where the product in or outwear form represents or symbolizes one's identity. For fashion consumers, this decision-making process is much more than a functional decision involving a piece of cloth, but social identity construction based on consumer culture.

Johnstone & Lindh (2022) also note that modern consumer purchase decisions incorporate an ethical component into purchase decisions, and that many people and especially those in young age segments are concerned with sustainability. Since consumers are becoming more conscious of the problems affecting the environment and the society, there is usually increased concern on the ethical impacts of production like the effects on the environment. Hence, the consumer purchase decision criteria in fashion is no longer just physiognomic preference and the financial strength but also a social propensity.

Similar to Venciute et al. (2023), the congruence between influencers and followers is highlighted as important as consumers' adoption intentions are influenced by perception of values similarity with influencers they are following. This results in value convergence, or more precisely, value alignment, which creates trust and, therefore, promotes consumer action based on recommendations.

1.1.2 Influencer Marketing

Based on current research and trends, influencer marketing is best described as a business model where a company works with key persons of a target market to market solutions within that market. Chetioui et al., (2020) explain that IM in the fashion industry uses influencer personalities as role models who share user-like content that appeals to the consumer and creates an intention to purchase. Recall that Johnstone and Lindh (2022) consider influencer marketing as another way of changing consumers' behavior and making the latter more sustainable; thus, the role of promotion and information dissemination goes hand in hand. The narrow definition of influencer marketing of promoting brands and products on various forums by influencers is expanded to incorporate the part played by influencers in creating awareness and persuading the target consumers to engage in desired activism. Finally, influencer and follower similarity is one of the elements of effective influencer marketing, according to Venciute et al. (2023). It is the match of perceived values and perceived beliefs between influencers and followers, which adds credibility to influencers and increases the chances of converting the transmitted messages into purchase intentions. Crisafulli and Singh (2022) have described influencer marketing in B2B contexts as a reliance on the stated influencer's expertise and skills, which are critical in the creation of trust, specifically in contexts which require clients to have significant amounts of prior knowledge. According to this perspective, the author argues that the effectiveness of influencer marketing often depends on the type of expertise of the influencer when addressing audiences in professional or technical disciplines.

1.2 Problem Statement

The fashion industry as a whole is in the process of changing as consumer awareness of the need to create more sustainable products rises. People have more disposable income and better access to credit and hence fashion is one of the most important signs of identity. However, the fast fashion business model has created deep social and environmental issues, which mean that change has to happen. For this reason, influencer marketing is now one of the powerful ways to make the consumers navigate to better choices as influencers control opinions.

The biggest issue is that brands often fail to determine who the appropriate influencers to promote their product or service are, and are they on the same wavelength as the company's target demographic. Every organization faces the challenge of identifying influencers with a good standing of promoting products in the market and at the same time representing a given brand. This misalignment can and does lead to problems of communication or indeed lack of communication between the consumer and the producer as well as investor, eroding trust and affecting purchasing decision.

Furthermore, there is a lack of knowledge about the influence that an influencer's credibility or promotional engagement rate and other factors may have an impact on consumer choices. I believe this is a big mistake that brands make concerning influencer marketing because they may not know how to capitalize on it properly.

Therefore, the problem that needs to be solved in this research is to explore the connection between influencer marketing and consumer purchase decision in fashion industry. The purpose of the study is to find out which factors define the ability of influencers to influence the purchasing decisions and to explain how the use of this marketing approach might contribute to the development of more sustainable consumption behavior.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research methodology adopts a literature review method in order to assess the extent of the influence of the influencer marketing on consumer purchase intention decision within the fashion industry. For this purpose, the study will gather published articles, case studies, and industry reports by peer-reviewed scholars with the interest of the study in relation to influencers and their impact on

consumer behaviour with reference to sustainable fashion. The literature review will subsequently focus on aspects such as credibility of influencers, their compatibility with the brand and the relation between these two aspects and clients' purchase decisions. In doing so, the research seeks to combine data from various sources to provide recommendations on how brands participating in influencer marketing should operate optimally. This literature review will help in enhancing the understanding of effectiveness of influencer marketing strategies for sustainable fashion consumption..

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

FINDINGS

From the analysis and literature conducted in this study on influencer marketing within the fashion industry and its effect on consumer behavior the following findings were made: First of all, it could be said that influencers have a strong impact on consumer behavioral intentions in the fashion sector, especially in the process of producing and sharing content that is related to their followers' values (Chetioui et al., 2020). Moreover, influencers should be involved in creating awareness of sustainable fashion so that consumers will begin to factor in the impacts of their decisions on both society and the environment (Johnstone & Lindh, 2022). It seems that congruence between the influencers and followers increases the connection between influencer marketing and consumer buying behavior. Finally, the content that an influencer shares should be liked by most of the followers because the follower is more likely to trust the influencer with similar values (Venciute et al., 2023). However, in the B2B case, both credibility and competence influence the decisions made as far as choosing the vendor or supplier (Crisafulli & Singh, 2022).

DISCUSSION

From these consumer research findings, it is evident that influencers significantly determine consumption and B2C purchase intentions but are also significant in B2B markets. Sustainability thematic fashion influencers therefore work as agents of change on the aspects of fashion consumption within the elaborate fast fashion value channel and can play a significant role in informing the consumers. Accordingly, as the focus on sustainability becomes more and more critical, it has emerged that the cooperation between companies and influencers is crucial; the company's values should correspond with the values of the influencer to guarantee customer retention and trust (Venciute et al., 2023). Moreover, the study of Crisafulli & Singh (2022) in the B2B context establish that competence of influencers affects purchase decisions, providing clues for the strategic vision of the marketing managers that have to take into account the experience the influencers when selecting them. Thus, this research contributes to the advancement of both sector's influencer marketing approaches and offers managerial recommendations that will help companies enhance their brand recognition and consumers' conversion rates based on proper influencer marketing tactics. Therefore, this research contributes not only to knowledge about influencer use in fashion marketing communication but also underlines one of the crucial aspects when choosing the right influencer for achieving the desired influence on sustainable consumption.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on this analysis, fashion brands focusing on collaborations should choose influencers who really share the same values as brands and support sustainability. Instructions for creating guidelines and strategies on choosing and evaluating influencers in terms of credibility, level of engagement, and values also improve influencer marketing strategies in marketing teams. Having influencers support the brand's sustainability efforts and goals creates a better relationship between the company and the consumer. Thus, concertized awareness of the influence of authenticity of influencers on the effectiveness of such influencers in the persuasion of consumers into environmentally sustainable fashion purchases is needed

to better devise the relevant marketing strategies capable of spearheading a shift from the current uncongenial environmentally unsustainable culture of apparel consumption.

CONCLUSION

In this research, influencer marketing is identified to have a significant impact of consumer purchase intentions in the fashion sector. Since fashion is a means of personal endorsement, it is critical for brands to find the right partner in influencing. Through the study, it is established that compatible, influencers improve brand credibility and trust and hence sustainable consumption practices. Further, the research provides insights into the problems that brands encounter making correct decisions about influencer marketing in changing environments of social media platforms. This is why in an attempt to change prospects into actual buyers, brands should shift their agendas to being genuine. Hence, based on the determinant of influencer effectiveness as fan engagement and perceived congruence brands can enhance the application of influencer marketing to affect customer purchase decision on fashion.

Future Research

In the fashion industry, future research must consider the effects of various kinds of influencers regarding consumer buying behaviour. Therefore, it might be useful to study such aspects as the relation between the format of the shared content, its authenticity and the values that brand adheres to. Also, research on regions and directions on how influencer marketing response differs across demographics may be useful for optimizing such strategies. Finally, to fill these gaps, new longitudinal investigations may follow shifts in the consumer attitude to the influencer marketing, specifically in terms of sustainable and ethical initiatives within the fashion industry over time.

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